

RAPID VOLUMETRIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF MERCURY, COPPER, ARSENIC, ETC. IN COMPLEX MIXTURES SUCH AS ANTIFOULING PIGMENTS. PART I

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A new iodine-iodide method for estimation of certain mercuric compounds has been described in which both iodine and potassium iodide enter into the reaction. The method is fairly accurate, cheap and comparatively quick and is also applicable in presence of other substances like Zn, Fe, Cu, Pb, As particularly in commercial analyses.

The problem of rapid estimation of mercuric oxide was taken up in connection with the analysis of some antifouling pigments in which mercuric oxide was added as a toxic ingredient along with copper and arsenic compounds. As this pigment may also have chloride as a contaminant, the direct volumetric estimation of mercuric compounds by ammonium thiocyanate method is not suitable unless mercury is separated out as HgS and then dissolved in H₂SO₄ (conc.) and KNO₃ (Naish¹). The method of titration in HCl solution by KI solution in presence of HNO₃ affords only a rough estimation.² The British Pharmacopoeia method³ for the estimation of HgCl₂ is generally applicable to relatively pure substances. On the other hand, the gravimetric ethylenediamine method⁴, though rapid in presence of Cu, As, etc., is not so if Fe is present, and the gravimetric HgS method⁵ is a long and expensive procedure and is also not very reliable in presence of both Cu and As (cf. Hillebrand and Lundell⁶).

The possibility of volumetric estimation of HgO by titrating with iodine solution in KI in presence of NaHCO₃ has been investigated, and under certain conditions found successful.

The titration with iodine-iodide solution, using starch as an internal indicator, can be done at room temperature. In this, both elemental iodine and the iodide enter into the reaction, whereas in ordinary iodimetry the concentration of iodine alone is the vital factor. Hence, iodine-iodide solution is standardised against a known mercuric chloride or mercuric oxide solution prepared as mentioned below. The sample must also be treated exactly as in the standardisation. The mechanism of reactions is presumably as :

In this estimation it is essential to work as far as possible under uniform conditions, if concordant results are to be obtained. The titration must be carried out slowly, and the solution must be thoroughly shaken throughout the titration otherwise low values may be obtained. The end-point is sharp, definite and permanent. At the end-point, the red HgI_2 suspension, formed during titration, becomes darkened by bluish violet tinge. The bluish violet colour will not disappear on shaking when the end-point is reached and it will deepen more with further addition of the iodine-iodide solution. The presence of Zn , Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} and Pb compounds in moderate quantities will not interfere with the estimation. Mercuric oxide and mercuric chloride have also been successfully assayed by this method with fairly high accuracy.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of iodine-iodide solution.—Pure iodine (A.R., 6.34 to 6.35 g.) was weighed in a weighing bottle and 10.0 g of KI, in a tared small beaker. The latter was then dissolved in 15-20 ml. of distilled water, iodine carefully introduced from the weighing bottle into the KI solution and stirred in the cold until all the iodine was dissolved. Immediately the solution was transferred to a glass-stoppered flask (1 litre). The volume was made up to the mark with distilled water and the solution stored in a dark place.

Standardisation of iodine-iodide solution.—Mercuric chloride of purity 99.3%, as checked by standard gravimetric method, was accurately weighed out (1.5 g.) in a 500 ml. conical flask, 1 : 3 HCl (30 ml.) was added into it and the flask after being covered with a watch glass was placed on a hot plate (40° - 50°) for 5 minutes. It was then cooled, diluted to about 200 ml. with distilled water and stirred well. When mercuric chloride had dissolved completely, the solution was transferred quantitatively to a 500 ml. flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. This solution (25 ml. or 50 ml.) was taken in a 500 ml. conical flask and diluted to about 150-200 ml. (or 250-300 ml.) with distilled water. The solution was neutralised with pure sodium bicarbonate solution and then saturated with solid sodium bicarbonate, a few lumps of which always remaining in excess. 1% Starch solution (2-3 ml. per 100 ml. of the test solution) was added and then it was titrated slowly with iodine-iodide solution, shaking thoroughly all throughout, to the definite and stable bluish violet colour. A blank test was always carried out taking the same volume of distilled water saturated with sodium bicarbonate. The volume of iodine-iodide solution required in the blank titration was deducted from the volume required in the original titration. The mercuric oxide value of 1 ml. of iodine-iodide solution was thus determined. It is important to carry out this standardisation for each set of experiments,

Titration of mercuric chloride in solutions of different molar concentrations with iodine-iodide solution.—Five solutions (0.005M, 0.01M, 0.015M, 0.02M and 0.025M, approx) of mercuric chloride (99.3%, known sample) were prepared exactly as stated above. Iodine-iodide solution was freshly prepared for the titrations. The variations of the results obtained by this method are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Conc. of HgCl ₂ soln. (99.3%)	Vol. of test soln.	Vol. of I ₂ -iodide soln.	HgCl ₂ in g. equiv. to 1 ml. I ₂ -iodide soln.	Average value.
1.358 g./litre (0.005M)	70 ml.	6.95 ml.	0.013582	0.013509
	70	7.00	0.013485	
	50	5.00	0.013485	
	50	5.00	0.013485	
2.716 g./litre (0.01M)	50	10.00	0.013485	0.013464
	50	10.00	0.013485	
	40	8.05	0.013401	
	40	8.00	0.013485	
4.074 g./litre (0.015M)	40	11.95	0.013541	0.013532
	40	11.90	0.013598	
	25	7.50	0.013495	
	25	7.50	0.013495	
5.432 g./litre (0.02M)	30	11.95	0.013541	0.013513
	30*	11.95	0.013541	
	25	10.0	0.013485	
	25	10.0	0.013485	
6.790 g./litre (0.025 M)	25	12.55	0.013432	0.013459
	25	12.55	0.013432	
	20	10.0	0.013485	
	20	10.0	0.013485	

Determination of HgO.—A known weight of the sample was taken and a solution was prepared exactly as stated under HgCl₂ solution using a minimum quantity of HCl and filtering, if necessary. An aliquot volume of the solution was then titrated with iodine-iodide solution in the same way as the standard solution described above. The mercuric oxide value of 1 ml. of iodine-iodide solution was also determined by titrating against a known sample, as described previously. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

HgO taken.	Other substances added.	HgO found.	Diff.	% Error.
0.04965 g.	Nil	0.049675 g	+0.000025 g	+0.05
0.04960	"	0.049675	+0.000075	+0.15
0.09930	"	0.099350	+0.00005	+0.05
0.09920	"	0.099080	-0.00012	-0.1
0.19860	"	0.19924	+0.00064	+0.3
0.19840	"	0.19960	+0.0012	+0.6
0.04965	ZnO 0.05 g	0.049135	-0.000515	-1.0
0.09930	" 0.1	0.099081	-0.000219	-0.2
0.04965	Red oxide 0.05	0.049405	-0.000245	-0.5
0.09930	" 0.1	0.099621	+0.000321	+0.3
0.04965	CuO 0.05	0.049545	+0.000295	+0.6
0.09930	" 0.1	0.099891	+0.000591	+0.6
0.04965	White lead 0.05	0.049405	-0.000245	-0.5
0.09930	" 0.1	0.099351	+0.000051	+0.05

Note: The total acid used in dissolving the material should be minimum, usually not exceeding 3 ml. conc. HCl in the volume of the test solution before neutralisation with NaHCO_3 . The best results have been obtained by using the aliquot volume of the solution containing about 0.1 g. HgO for titration. With higher amounts of HgO the red colour that develops is apt to cause a little over-titration.

Procedure for determining mercury in composite pigments containing arsenious and cuprous compounds.—A mixture was weighed out accurately (5.0 g.) in a 500 ml. conical flask and 10-11 ml. HCl (conc.) added. (This amount of HCl in conjunction with HNO_3 added subsequently will completely dissolve Zn, Hg, As and Cu and a small portion of the red oxide). The flask was covered with a watch glass and stirred well, and then placed on a hot plate (40° - 50°) for 5 minutes. HNO_3 (conc., colorless; 3-3.5 ml.) was added after cooling and the content stirred well. The flask was again placed on the hot plate for 10 minutes, cooled and the content diluted to about 200 ml. with distilled water. The solution was heated to boiling, cooled and filtered in a 500 ml. measuring flask. The residue consisting of red oxide only was washed well (chloride-free). The volume of the filtrate was made up to the mark with distilled water. Aliquot volumes of the solution were then titrated as usual with the standard iodine-iodide solution, after saturating with sodium bicarbonate.

The standard solution of mercuric chloride (or oxide) for the standardisation of iodine-iodide solution was prepared exactly as described above using 10-11 ml. HCl (conc.) and 3-3.5 ml. HNO_3 (conc.).

The mercury content of the sample was also estimated by ethylene-diamine method (gravimetric) for comparison. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

	HgO in pigment prepared in laboratory.	Other substances present.				HgO found by		Difference.	
		Red oxide.	Cu ₂ O.	As ₂ O ₃ .	ZnO.	I ₂ -iodide method.	Ethylene-diamine method.	I ₂ -iodide method.	Ethylene-diamine method.
1	2.48%	55%	30%	2.5%	10%	2.5%	2.34%	+0.02%	-0.14%
2	4.96	50	30	5	10	5.05	4.74	+0.09	-0.22
3	9.93	45	30	5	10	9.95	9.76	+0.02	-0.17
4	19.86	30	30	10	10	19.98	20.0	+0.12	+0.14
5	Pigment (unknown) (extracted from paint)		...	...	...	9.18	9.10	-	...
6	"	...	...	...	...	6.20	6.08	...	...
7	"	...	...	...	...	6.97	7.10	...	...
8	"	...	...	...	...	24.86	24.61	...	...

Note. 1. In the case of mixtures containing high percentage of mercury and copper (e.g. sample No. 4) the bluish violet end-point may be difficult to recognise because of the masking action of the red HgI₂ precipitate and the blue colour of the copper solution. To obviate this difficulty a small aliquot volume should be taken, so that the titre does not exceed 10.0 ml.

2. In dissolving antifouling pigment, hydrochloric acid and nitric acid are so adjusted that all arsenic compounds present are oxidised to pentavalent state and at the same time a major portion of ferric oxide, the presence of which in excess is undesirable, remains undissolved. But the filtrate should be acidic to litmus.

3. Normally the oxidation treatment with 3 to 3.5 ml. of conc. HNO₃ at the time of dissolving the pigment will convert trivalent arsenic into the pentavalent state. However, as trivalent arsenic interferes with the estimation of Hg by the iodine-iodide method, it is important to ensure its absence (*vide infra*).

The test solution (25 ml.) is taken in a small conical flask and made alkaline with saturated solution of pure NaHCO₃. It is then treated with excess (about 1 g.) of KI in the form of a 2% solution (red precipitate appears and completely disappears). In this way mercury is made into a complex which does not act with iodine. This solution should produce blue colour with starch and iodine solution, indicating the absence of trivalent arsenic.

DISCUSSION

As will be seen from the results obtained in the titration of the mercuric compounds in pure form or in admixture with other ingredients by the iodine-iodide method used in this experiment, the procedure may well replace the gravimetric HgS or volumetric thiocyanate methods, particularly in commercial analysis. In all the titrations, the results of which are recorded in Tables I and II, the error ranges between 0.05 and 1% which is well within the limit permissible in industrial analysis. The method has the special advantage of saving much time and cost, being complete in less than 2 hours. It may, however, be pointed out that the presence of nitrate and small amount of sulphate will not interfere with the estimation.

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